

Intellectual Capital: A Political Game-Changer in Pakistan's Startup Ecosystem

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Author Affiliation:

¹Institute of Business and Health Management, Dow University of Health Sciences, Karachi, Pakistan.

²Government College University Hyderabad (GCUH), Hyderabad, Sindh 71000, Pakistan.

³Shaheed Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto University of Law, Karachi City, Sindh 75600, Pakistan.

***Corresponding author**

Institute of Business and Health Management, Dow University of Health Sciences, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: ammadagha786@gmail.com

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Agha Amad Nabi ^{1,2*}, Zartasha Shahzadah ¹, Fayaz Hussain Tunio ³, Aftab Mukhi ¹, Waqar A. Sethar ¹, Manthar Ali Bugti ¹

ABSTRACT

This research delves into an examination of the influence exerted by intellectual capital on the success of startups operating within Pakistan's burgeoning market. The study places a particular emphasis on the pivotal roles played by human capital, relational capital, and structural capital in nurturing and bolstering the entrepreneurial ecosystem within this context. While foreign and domestic investments undoubtedly hold significance, their capacity to drive sustainable growth in isolation may prove insufficient. Therefore, the cultivation and management of intellectual capital emerge as critical determinants of startup success. At its core, this research seeks to ascertain the precise manner in which the presence or absence of these dimensions of intellectual capital during the early stages of a startup's development can impact its subsequent success and overall performance. Moreover, it endeavors to differentiate and delineate the effects on startups with operational histories under five years from those that have surpassed the five-year threshold. In pursuit of these overarching objectives, the research adopts a questionnaire-based approach, consisting of a meticulously designed set of 18 queries. This instrument serves as a means to assess the innovative capabilities of startups, which constitute the dependent variable under examination. By employing this methodological framework, the study aspires to unveil the intricate dynamics and interactions between the various components of intellectual capital and their divergent impacts on startups of varying operational durations. This study contributes significantly to enhancing our comprehension of Pakistan's startup landscape, offering a profound illumination of the indispensable roles played by human capital, relational capital, and structural capital in shaping the innovation potential of startups.

Keywords: Startups, Intellectual capital, human capital, structural capital, relational capital, Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept denoting valuable knowledge within an organization is referred to as "intellectual capital." Its primary constituents encompass human capital, structural capital, and customer capital (Jordão & Novas, 2022). Although a universally accepted definition of intellectual capital remains elusive, scholars have endeavored to delineate their respective domains. Intellectual capital, characterized as intangible assets, does not find representation in a company's financial statements, yet it exerts a favorable influence on its performance and overall success (Gharib et al., 2023; Yaseen et al., 2023).

Renowned experts and researchers frequently identify intellectual capital as a pivotal source of a company's competitive advantage. This is particularly evident in companies where intellectual capital constitutes an intangible investment, typically associated with research and development (R&D), innovation, knowledge cultivation, infrastructure development, which collectively serve as the most critical source of corporate performance (Rehman et al. 2022; Suki et al., 2023). Notably, distinctions exist within the definition of human capital. Human capital places greater emphasis on amalgamating individual attributes with the collective strength of a company's workforce. These attributes encompass knowledge, skill, behavior, energy, and employee commitment, fostering a culture of information sharing, teamwork, and alignment with corporate objectives. Human capital primarily comprises the individuals who steer the management of a company. In contrast, structural capital operates under the company's control and governance (Ayinde et al., 2022). Over the years, the significance of information disclosed in corporate financial statements has escalated. Financial statements serve as vital conduits for corporate communication, and contemporary corporate communication is characterized by its strategic orientation, emphasizing futuristic perspectives, including intellectual capital (IC) reporting (Affes & Affes, 2023). This shift in paradigm can be attributed to various factors such as shifts in the economy, advancements in information technology, and evolving accounting standards, among others. Firms have come to recognize the relevance of reporting on intellectual capital as it contributes to enhanced profitability. Furthermore, human, structural, and relational capitals are acknowledged as key determinants of entrepreneurial expectations among startups (Wang et al., 2023). Skoog (2003) underscores the significance of a firm's intangible assets in value creation, emphasizing the need for greater information disclosure. However, the extent of such disclosures hinges on the unique requirements of individual companies and the expectations of stakeholders (Giacosa et al., 2017). This relationship between human, structural, and relational capitals and startup expectations has been explored through diverse measurement methodologies across several countries. The Value Added Intellectual Coefficient (VAIC) provides a convenient means of assessing a company's IC proficiency. Regrettably, the relationship between intellectual capital and firm performance remains inadequately examined within the context of Pakistan. Pakistan's startup ecosystem has experienced remarkable growth, ascending to the 75th position globally and securing the 2nd position in the South Asian region, as indicated by the "Global Startups Ecosystem Index 2021." Lahore stands out as the highest-ranked city in Pakistan for startup activity, rising 14 positions to claim the 257th spot globally and the 4th position in South Asia.

Pakistan, the fifth most populous country, boasts a population of 200 million English-speaking, educated youth, facilitating global startup interactions. In 2020, Pakistan witnessed a 97 percent surge in venture capital funding, contributing significantly to its evolution as a startup ecosystem hub, as reported in the 2021 Emerging Venture Markets Report. The Pakistan Startup Ecosystem Report 2019 highlights a substantial increase in business startup activity between 2012 and 2019 (Ikram et al., 2019; Tanweer et al., 2023). During this period, the number of major incubators/accelerators surged from two to 24, formal investors and funding sources increased by 20, and the count of co-working spaces reached 80. The emergence of business incubators, accelerators, and co-working spaces across Pakistan, some with support from the Federal Government's National R&D Fund, underscores this growth. Despite the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, Pakistan anticipates consumer spending to reach \$360 billion by 2027. Presently, Pakistan hosts over 800 startups, and it is estimated that these startups secured investments through 141 deals from 2015 to 2020. Out of these deals, 19 remain undisclosed, attributing \$178 million to 122 deals. This surge has been bolstered by infrastructure development and policy measures (Soomro et al., 2019). Pakistan has witnessed substantial growth in internet adoption over the last five years, driven by affordability, with 1.5 GB costing less than a dollar. This has resulted in 103 million internet subscribers, creating an expansive and accessible target market for startups. Pakistan boasts an abundance of tech talent, with 400,000 software engineers and 20,000 computer science and information technology graduates entering the workforce annually. The Government of Pakistan has established a \$75 million fund for entrepreneurs and small startups at the State Bank of Pakistan (SBP). However, it is worth noting that 90% of startups fail each year (Abro et al., 2019). The Pakistani economy predominantly relies on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which constitute more than 99 percent of all businesses. These SMEs are akin to startups in their nascent stages. Therefore, if intellectual capital plays a role in the success or failure of these startups, this study holds significance in shedding light on this matter and offering insights to benefit future startups.

The primary objective of this study is to examine the relationship between intellectual capital, specifically human, structural, and relational capital, and its role as an investment tool in evaluating and deciphering the determinants behind the success of startups in Pakistan.

2. Literature Review

The prevailing body of literature pertaining to intellectual capital predominantly emanates from research institutions situated in economically advanced nations, such as the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada, Australia, and Sweden. A multitude of scholars have diligently conducted their inquiries within the ambit of these prosperous economies, yielding noteworthy insights into the significant nexus between efficacious intellectual capital management and the prosperity of enterprises (Alliou & Mourdi, 2023). In recognition of the widespread acknowledgement of the constructive impact exerted by intellectual capital within developed regions, a burgeoning corpus of scholarly investigations has emerged, devoted to the examination of the intellectual capital paradigm within enterprises operating within developing and underdeveloped economies (Khalique et al., 2015). Researchers concluded that intellectual capital is a major source for organizations to gain competitive benefits in knowledge based economy (Ausat et al., 2022; Asiaei et al., 2023). Al-Tit et al., (2022) categorized intellectual capital into human capital, customer capital, and structural capital. Numerous studies show that the degree of education of the entrepreneurs is positively connected with the firm's survival and growth, but experience appears to be an equally significant human capital component (Zane, 2023; Grilli et al., 2023). Business experiences can supplement the

knowledge base gained in schools, universities, or continuing education programs. Some of these experiences are related to entrepreneurs' earlier involvement in managing jobs. Organizations are more likely to flourish when entrepreneurs previously held management positions in another company. In this regard, some authors have focused their emphasis on earlier start-up experience or the knowledge obtained through operating a corporation in the past (Ziakis et al., 2022; Bařka et al., 2022). There is empirical evidence that investments in intangibles, such as knowledge or brands, are economically beneficial to firms. Often, these intangibles are denoted by the term "intellectual capital" (IC) (Bronnenberg et al., 2022). Three features have recently been stressed in IC frameworks. First, the growing relevance of IC management necessitates a change in the way corporate executives operate their businesses. In today's competitive market, knowledge has become a vital resource that organizations must master, and in order to manage knowledge, corporate managers require information that standard accounting systems and financial reports do not provide. As a result, non-financial measures for measuring intangible assets are desperately needed (Al-Omoush et al., 2022).

Building upon previous research highlighting the role of intellectual capital in business functionality, it is posited that intellectual capital exerts a positive influence on business expansion and efficiency.

Hypothesis 1: Human capital exhibits a positive and significant association with the organizational performance of startups.

Hypothesis 2: Relational capital demonstrates a positive and significant association with the organizational performance of startups.

Hypothesis 3: Structural capital manifests a positive and significant association with the organizational performance of startups.

2.1. Theoretical Framework

2.1.1. Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory

This theory expounds upon the likelihood of a firm's success, drawing upon a synthesis of external and internal resources. Externally, the attainment of firm success is intricately tied to the prospect of securing external business capital. Concurrently, the theory accords paramount significance to the internal resources at a firm's disposal, particularly emphasizing the expertise and skill set possessed by its management team as pivotal determinants of success (Yang et al., 2022). Within the framework of this perspective, an organization's performance stands predicated upon the judicious allocation and utilization of its resources, effectively transforming them into competencies that enable it to vie with other enterprises. Underpinning this viewpoint is the assertion that Intellectual Capital emerges as the preeminent internal resource, possessing a pivotal role in facilitating the firm's entry into competitive arenas (Martin-Rios et al., 2022). This theoretical construct, known as the Resource-Based View (RBV), serves as a conceptual bridge, linking a firm's intrinsic capabilities, i.e., what it excels at, with the external market dynamics, encompassing both the demands of prospective customers and the offerings presented by competitors.

2.1.2. Knowledge-Based theory

In response to these challenges, the capabilities dynamics perspective has emerged as an extension of the resource-based view. It posits that the survival and competitive edge of organizations stem from their capacity to cultivate knowledge and expertise to adapt to the evolving environmental demands (Permatasari et al., 2023). In the contemporary landscape, knowledge assumes a central role in driving organizational success, with a widespread acknowledgment that the acquisition and application of new knowledge are pivotal in gaining and sustaining competitive advantages. Furthermore, it is widely accepted that knowledge serves as the primary factor of production in a knowledge-based economy. Knowledge-based assets are instrumental in the value creation process (Ouriques et al., 2023).

In the context of a knowledge-based economy, an organization's capabilities are fundamentally rooted in knowledge, necessitating that managers possess a keen understanding of the specific capabilities required to maintain their competitive advantages.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Research Design and Settings

This study employs a qualitative research methodology, which involves the synthesis of data from various sources, including articles, journals, and papers, to generate new insights tailored to the research topic. Furthermore, quantitative analysis using a survey questionnaire will be conducted to obtain fresh data. The survey questionnaire consists of four questions for each variable: Human Capital (HC), Structural Capital (SC), Relational Capital (RC), and their interrelationship with Intellectual Capital (IC). All questions are structured using a Likert Scale, a rating system that gauges respondents' agreement or disagreement with statements, typically ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree."

3.1.1. Inclusion Criteria

This study includes businesses that have emerged in Pakistan over the past decade, specifically from around 2010 to 2022, and remain operational.

3.1.2. Exclusion Criteria

The study excludes non-Pakistani businesses and inactive businesses as of 2022. Businesses that began operations in 2023 are not considered. Dichotomous scales, which offer only two opposing response options (e.g., Yes-No or True-False), are avoided due to their inability to capture neutral responses or yield a mean value. Additionally, any businesses that underwent changes in their legal status, ownership, or were involved in mergers or acquisitions have been excluded from the study sample.

3.2. Sampling Technique

The study employed a survey targeting a sample size of sixteen startup businesses, which was conducted through a Google survey.

3.3. Sample Size Estimation

The sample size was determined to consist of sixteen startup businesses.

3.4. Study Parameters

This study exclusively concentrates on new businesses, regardless of whether they are publicly listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX).

3.5. Data Collection

The primary aim of the current research was to investigate the influence of intellectual capital on the likelihood of success and sustainability of start-up businesses in the long term. The study utilized panel data collected from 16 newly established start-ups in Pakistan. Due to the scarcity of well-documented start-ups, the selection criteria for the inclusion of companies extended to those established within the past five years. This timeframe was chosen to align with the established success criteria of start-ups, which typically require functionality for at least 3 to 42 months, as per the standards set forth by Hormiga et al. (2011).

Following extensive communication with the selected firms, a total of 17 completed questionnaires were received, all of which were deemed valid for analysis. Each questionnaire was completed by a manager within the respective business who was actively involved in the daily operations of the firm. Preferably, this individual was either the owner or held a key position within the human resources department. Furthermore, all the participating firms had been established between the years 2017 and 2022 in Pakistan, ensuring a consistent economic and fiscal context for the analyzed units.

The dependent variable under scrutiny in this research is the success of these start-ups, measured by indicators such as their highest profitability year, market expansion, and their overall contribution to intellectual capital. Consequently, the questionnaire posed a series of questions to entrepreneurs, utilizing dichotomous, closed multiple-choice, and nominal questions. These questions aimed to ascertain the specific type of intellectual capital upon which each start-up relied most heavily, the sector in which they operated, the year in which their start-up was most profitable, and which intellectual capital variable played the most significant role in this success.

As for the independent variables, they were assessed on a 5-point Likert scale, gauging the level of importance that each new firm attributed to their human, structural, and relational capital investments, ranging from very low to very high.

3.6. Operational Definitions

3.6.1. Independent Variables

- I. **Human Capital (HC):** Human Capital encompasses various aspects related to the employees within an organization. This includes their training, development, and their overall contribution to organizational growth and value creation. It's important to note that having a large workforce with good qualifications and experience does not necessarily equate to efficiency or value creation. Efficiency primarily depends on how these employees contribute to the organization's value creation process. Human Capital is seen as a production factor in the organization and comprises intelligence, knowledge, and skills that give each organization its distinct character. Individuals within the organization are considered elements capable of learning, innovating, thinking creatively, initiating change, and driving innovation. Human Capital is crucial for long-term performance and acts as a source of innovation and strategic renewal within organizations.
- II. **Structural Capital:** Structural Capital pertains to the organizational structure, its vision, mission, infrastructure, intellectual property owned by the firm, and the institutional knowledge created and owned by the organization. This knowledge is often stored in databases, manuals, and other forms of documentation. This type of capital encompasses work processes, organizational norms, technological processes, know-how, branding, and more. In essence, it represents the tangible elements directly linked to the development of the organization's technical system. In the context of higher education institutions, it includes explicit knowledge related to the internal processes of disseminating, communicating, and managing scientific and technical knowledge within universities.
- III. **Relational Capital:** Relational Capital, also referred to as Customer Capital, centers around the contribution of clientele to organizational growth. This includes factors such as the revenue generated from significant customers, their commitment levels indicated by repeat business, networking, and similar interactions. Relational Capital encompasses the knowledge incorporated into the organization and its people as a result of the value derived from maintaining relationships with various stakeholders and society in general. It consists of two components: business capital, which relates to the value of relationships maintained with key stakeholders closely linked to the organization's core business processes, and social capital, which pertains to the value of relationships with other social agents in the organization's environment.

3.6.2. Dependent Variable

- I. **Start-ups:** Start-ups are defined as innovative ventures that may benefit from the incorporation of intellectual capital and accelerator programs. Accelerators are considered an essential component of start-up infrastructure in innovative economies. The success of a start-up is measured by its ability to achieve high profitability and expand its business beyond its initial scope based on customer acquisition, including the influence of Intellectual Capital.

3.7. Econometric Framework

The research employed a multivariate regression approach to evaluate the influence of explanatory variables on the response variable, thereby facilitating the derivation of meaningful policy implications. The principal equation of the study is articulated as follows:

$$\text{Start-ups} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{HC} + \beta_2\text{SC} + \beta_3\text{RC} + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Where, "Start-ups" represent the dependent variable, while β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 representing coefficients for the respective independent variables (HC, SC, RC), and ϵ representing the error term in the model.

The equation serves as the foundation for the statistical analysis in this study. Figure 1 depicts the study's conceptual framework. It aims to determine the extent to which the availability of human capital, structural capital, and relational capital impacts the

performance of start-ups, especially concerning the influence of accelerator programs. This study employs multiple regression analysis to provide quantitative evidence of the impact of accelerator programs and certain technologies on the performance and success of startups in Pakistan.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

Source: Author’s extract.

4. Results and Discussion

A paired sample t-test was employed to compare the success of start-ups with each of the three variables (HC, SC, RC), as depicted in Table 1. The standard deviation between the pairs 1, 2, and 3 was examined. The results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference between the samples. In other words, this study employed the formula for degrees of freedom ($Df = n1 + n2 + n3 - 2$) to determine the critical value based on the null hypothesis (H_0), as illustrated in Table 1. The critical value should approximate 2. Since the values for degrees of freedom (df) fall below 2, it suggests that the null hypothesis can be accepted. Consequently, this signifies that there is a statistically significant relationship between the independent variables (HC, SC, and RC) and the success of start-ups (STARTUPS).

Table 1: Paired Samples Statistics

Pairs	Variables	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	HC	3.895	16	.674	.168
	STARTUPS	2.808	16	.418	.104
Pair 2	SC	3.708	16	.868	.217
	STARTUPS	2.808	16	.418	.104
Pair 3	RC	3.375	16	.941	.235
	STARTUPS	2.808	16	.418	.104

Source: Author’s estimate.

Additional comprehensive statistical information can be found in Table 2, which pertains to the range, skewness, and kurtosis of the variables under investigation.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
HC	16	3.00	5.00	3.8958	.16865	.67461	.433	.564	-.563	1.091
SC	16	2.00	5.00	3.7083	.21704	.86816	-.337	.564	-.332	1.091
RC	16	2.00	5.00	3.3750	.23546	.94183	.503	.564	-.504	1.091
STARTUPS	16	2.27	3.80	2.8083	.10451	.41802	1.121	.564	.720	1.091
Intellectual capital	16	1.95	3.29	2.6667	.07629	.30516	-.191	.564	1.798	1.091
Valid N (listwise)	16									

Source: Author’s estimate.

Table 3 provides an insightful correlation analysis among the independent variables encompassing intellectual capital, aimed at discerning their significance and associations with the growth of start-up businesses. The numerical values contained within the cells denote the correlation coefficients characterizing the relationships between these variables. Notably, a correlation coefficient of 1 is observed along the diagonal, representing a perfect positive correlation of each variable with itself, as expected. Additionally, a correlation coefficient of 0.3 suggests a positive correlation between HC (Human Capital) and RC (Relational Capital). This indicates that as one variable increases, the other tends to increase as well, though the strength of this correlation is relatively weak. Furthermore, a correlation coefficient of 0.4 points to a positive correlation between Human Capital (HC) and Structural Capital (SC). This implies that as one variable increases, the other also tends to increase, and this relationship is characterized as moderately positive. The most significant finding is the correlation coefficient of 0.49, signifying a moderate positive correlation between Human Capital (HC) and Startup Growth. This result suggests that higher values of Human Capital are associated with higher levels of Startup Growth, indicating a potential positive influence of Human Capital on the growth of start-up businesses.

Table 3: Correlation Estimates

		HC	SC	RC	STARTUPS	Intellectual capital
HC	Pearson Correlation	1	.413	.310	.497	.411
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.112	.242	.050	.114
	N	16	16	16	16	16
SC	Pearson Correlation	.413	1	.161	.399	.615'
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.112		.552	.126	.011
	N	16	16	16	16	16
RC	Pearson Correlation	.310	.161	1	.786''	.722''
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.242	.552		.000	.002
	N	16	16	16	16	16
STARTUPS	Pearson Correlation	.497	.399	.786''	1	.674''
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.050	.126	.000		.004
	N	16	16	16	16	16
Intellectual capital	Pearson Correlation	.411	.615'	.722''	.674''	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.114	.011	.002	.004	
	N	16	16	16	16	16

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author's estimate.

Table 4 shows the regression estimates and found that the positive influence of relational capital, specifically customer capital, on the enhancement of start-up operations in Pakistan. Strong and enduring customer relationships were found to be positively correlated with improved operational efficiency, higher customer satisfaction levels, and enhanced financial performance. The implications of these findings for start-up entrepreneurs and business managers are profound. Firstly, it is imperative for entrepreneurs to recognize the strategic significance of cultivating and nurturing customer relationships from the inception of their ventures. Building and sustaining customer capital should be accorded a central role in the business strategy (Chaudhri et al., 2022). Secondly, the results underscore the value of investing in customer relationship management (CRM) systems and practices that facilitate the maintenance of long-term, mutually beneficial customer partnerships. This entails not only acquiring new customers but also ensuring their retention and loyalty through personalized services and communication (Lasrado et al., 2023). Lastly, the study underscores the importance of monitoring and evaluating key performance indicators (KPIs) related to customer capital. Regular assessment of customer satisfaction levels, loyalty, and referrals can provide valuable insights for strategic decision-making (Alzoubi et al., 2022).

Table 4: Regression Estimates

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations		
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part
1	(Constant)	.928	.411		2.260	.043			
	HC	.122	.107	.197	1.140	.277	.497	.313	.173
	SC	.099	.080	.206	1.238	.240	.399	.336	.188
	RC	.307	.071	.691	4.323	.001	.786	.780	.656

Source: Author's estimate

The statistical summary of the model reveals a robust level of association among the variables. The coefficient of determination denoted as R-squared, stands impressively at 0.723. This value signifies that approximately 72.3% of the variance observed in the dependent variable can be accounted for by the independent variables integrated into the model. Furthermore, the adjusted R squared value, calculated as 0.654, indicates a favorable balance between model complexity and its explanatory power, while accommodating the potential influence of additional variables. The model's predictive accuracy is significantly bolstered by a correlation coefficient (R) of 85%, representing a strong positive linear relationship between the variables under examination, as depicted in Table 5. Moreover, the standard error of 0.25 elucidates the average degree of dispersion observed in the values from the fitted values, providing insights into the model's precision. The substantial R squared change of 0.723 underscores the noteworthy contribution of the independent variables in elucidating the variations observed in the dependent variable, thus reaffirming the model's significance.

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.850 ^a	.723	.654	.24582	.723	10.458	3	12	.001

a. Predictors: (Constant), RC, SC, HC

Source: Author's estimate.

Table 6 shows the results from the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) offer valuable insights into the effectiveness of the regression model in elucidating the variability within the dataset. The regression component, contributing a sum of squares equal to 1.896, serves as an indicator of the overall variability accounted for by the regression model. The ANOVA results shed light on the equilibrium between the variance explained by the model and the unexplained variance in the data. The robust F statistic, along with its statistical significance, underscores the model's efficacy in capturing meaningful patterns and relationships inherent in the dataset. Through the dissection of variability into these distinct components, the ANOVA analysis furnishes a comprehensive comprehension of the model's performance and its ability to predict the dependent variable based on the independent variables. The significance level associated with the F statistic (0.001) implies that the observed F value is highly improbable to arise solely by chance. In essence, the F statistic attains a significant level of statistical significance at a very low threshold, indicating that the regression model, as a whole, carries substantive meaning and offers a better fit compared to a model without any predictors.

Table 6: ANOVA Estimates

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.896	3	.632	10.458	.001 ^a
	Residual	.725	12	.060		
	Total	2.621	15			

a. Predictors: (Constant), RC, SC, HC

b. Dependent Variable: STARTUPS

Source: Author's estimate.

The F statistic serves as a pivotal metric in assessing whether the variation observed in the dependent variable, as explained by this regression model, holds statistical significance. A higher F statistic value, coupled with a low p-value, signifies that the model provides meaningful insights into the relationship between the independent variable (startup growth) and the amalgamation of dependent variables (human capital, structural capital, and relational capital). This robust statistical approach bolsters the confidence in the model's ability to offer valuable insights into the intricate interplay of these variables and their impact on the growth of start-up businesses.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, the present study illuminates the pivotal role of relational capital, specifically customer capital, in augmenting start-up operations in Pakistan. Entrepreneurs and business leaders must recognize the potential advantages of investing in customer relationships and should integrate strategies for the development and maintenance of strong customer capital into their operational framework. By doing so, they can unlock a significant source of competitive advantage and foster sustained growth and success for their start-up ventures. A startup that boasts a skilled and knowledgeable workforce can effectively leverage its human capital. Highly competent employees bring innovative ideas and problem-solving capabilities, fostering a culture of creativity within the organization. Their adaptability equips the startup to navigate the ever-evolving market dynamics with agility. Furthermore, an adept team operates more efficiently, resulting in optimized processes and resource allocation. Continuous learning within the startup nurtures a dynamic

skill set, thereby reinforcing its competitiveness.

The establishment of robust relationships, both internal and external, is of paramount importance. Internally, cohesive teamwork promotes collaboration and aligns members with shared goals. Externally, building strong connections with suppliers, customers, investors, and mentors amplifies access to crucial resources, knowledge, and growth opportunities. Trustworthy networks can accelerate market entry, open doors to strategic partnerships, and offer valuable insights, ultimately enhancing the startup's credibility and growth potential. The structural capital of a startup, encompassing its setup, processes, systems, and intellectual property, is integral to its success. Efficient operational procedures streamline workflows and reduce inefficiencies, contributing to overall productivity. Well-organized knowledge management practices ensure that institutional memory is preserved, ensuring that intellectual assets endure beyond individual employees. Additionally, protected intellectual property, such as patents or proprietary technology, not only provides a competitive edge but also attracts potential investors.

This research significantly advances our comprehension of the pivotal role played by intangible assets, particularly the intellectual capacity of nascent businesses, in shaping their success. The findings firmly establish a robust correlation between intangible assets and the achievements of emerging firms. Specifically, the study underscores the profound impact of human capital, structural capital, and relational capital on the performance of businesses during their initial stages. These insights reinforce the widely acknowledged notion that entrepreneurs, armed with their expertise, competencies, innovative business models, and networking prowess, substantially amplify business profitability and facilitate both domestic and international expansion. Furthermore, this research provides supplementary evidence, highlighting that enterprises committed to cultivating strong relationships tend to not only experience accelerated growth but also realize amplified profits. This underscores the premise that fostering meaningful connections within the business ecosystem confers a distinct competitive edge, effectively propelling enterprises toward sustainable success.

Looking ahead to future research endeavors, it is recommended that subsequent studies delve into the linkages between assets that were not covered in this research. For instance, exploring the influence of intellectual programs on investing companies and accelerator programs could offer valuable insights. Moreover, introducing a moderator variable between intellectual capital and startup success factors could add complexity and depth to the analysis. Additionally, broadening the scope to consider additional factors influencing startup success would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of this multifaceted phenomenon.

Ethical approval

Not Applicable.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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